

A Comparative Analysis of Mean Time Spent on Activities by Gender Before and During COVID-19: Based on Time Use Survey for Pensioners of Division Bahawalpur, Pakistan

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
April 11, 2021

Accepted:
September 14, 2021

Keywords :

Time use, Pensioners,
Retirement, Covid-19

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5507772

Abstract

The objective of this study is to determine and compare the mean time spent on activities by male and female pensioners before and during Covid-19. The research study was conducted from February, 2019 to August 2020 in division Bahawalpur, Pakistan. The sample size was selected from the population of 10,919 retirees by the stratified random sampling technique. The analysis was done in R programming. The results of this study suggest that there were remarkable differences in time use of both genders before and during Covid-19, but sleeping/resting was the only activity on which both genders spent same amount of time.

Introduction

Time is the utmost valuable thing a man owns. No one can deny its importance in one's life, as according to a famous English proverb, "Time and tide wait for none". Time is needed in each and every phase of life. Time has a great influence on every aspect of a human's life. Our daily routine and experiences are also measured in respect of time. That is the main reason why the topic of time use is of great significance. Time use methodologies are related to people's lifestyle. The foremost concern of the time use survey is to have a clearer view of how people spend their time. It also offers an exclusive point of view about behaviours of people, their actual living standards, family life, personal life, social life and work life. Time use study gives a clear picture of the activities in which usually people are involved i.e., when, where and with whom they perform those activities. According to Merz (2002), time use is actually about aspects of a group of distinct activities and lifestyles. It is used to improve conventional, specific perspectives, persona contribution, spare time and social work. Nominally, it is a way of displaying day to day or week to week activities in which people are involved. Speaking in a maximal way, it demonstrates what activity people do, where and with whom they do that activity and what they feel. A moderate to high variation can be seen in the activities of people. Time use research can be piloted for various reasons. The leading cause of time use survey is to collect statistics regarding time spent in activities on a typical day. These statistics are then analyzed for the betterment of households. The analysis makes a way to improved social and economic policies. Time use studies are not only used to have a focus on social and economic factors, but it also has a wide-ranging scope. These studies have been used all the way through current and previous centuries to observe the subjective and objective traits of people. Time use study is an affair that examines the behaviour of individuals; it is also significant for one's awareness, development and perception of life. These surveys are conducted for exploring the daily physical activities, psychological wellbeing of the individuals, and analysis of nutrition-related to public health (Bauman, Bittman, & Gershuny, 2019).

People reaching to older ages have different set of activities as compared to other age groups. Additionally, after retirement, retirees involve themselves in various activities to keep themselves busy. Retirement brings significant changes in one's life. Agahi and Parker (2005) analyzed the changes in older Swedish resident's participation in leisure, over a time period of 10 years. The data was taken in 1992 and 2002 from people having age 77 years or more. It was observed that level of involvement in leisure activities was greater in later years. Women in later years were mostly involved in physical activities only. Most of the activities in which Swedish people participated were cultural and social. It was also seen that in 1992 health conditions were better, and in 2002 it got worse.

Retirement changes the perception of life. Involving in different activities gives meaning to their life or else he might be surrounded by depression. In life after retirement, things change forever and the central focus of life becomes leisure. Many of the retired people's concepts about leisure are not having anything to do. Lack of

motivation is the main source that affects the emotional and mental state and then gradually the physical health. A successful retired person balances his/her leisure over various other activities. Using data from time use survey, conducted in nine countries -Finland, Germany, Netherlands, Canada, the United States, Japan, the United Kingdom, Italy, Sweden- Gauthier and Smeeding (2003) aimed to show a variation at country-level in older adult's time use and the changes that occurred with increasing age in their time use. They concluded that with the passage of time, the amount of period for paid work was decreased. Time spent on personal and leisure activities was increased with age. There was no dissimilarity seen in activities through the countries, but there were differences in their use of time. Croda & Gonzalez-Chapela (2008) has described how time use surveys can be utilized for evaluating the wellbeing of older adults and how do they spend their time. The authors have conducted detailed research on the time being spent by the European elderly population. They provided a graphical representation for showing the number of elderly adults busy in market work, offering help, and caring for their grandchildren. The authors identified that the health of elderly adults significantly affects the way they spend their time. They also presented hourly representation of the activities carried out by older men and women. It was seen that most of the older adults spent most of their time in market work. Novak and Vute (2013) in their study about "Spending leisure time and activities in the third period of life" aimed to determine the preferred activities of women aged 65 years or above and including those women in several recreational and social activities. A sample of 32 women was taken from the two towns of Slovenia, named Kamnik and Domžale in 2006 and 2011. Their findings showed that most of the respondents spent their leisure watching TV, gardening, meeting relatives and reading.

Allocation of time for various daily life activities in a day is different for both genders. According to Kent and Stewart (2007), the time use of older Americans was highly affected by age. Their study was based on data taken from the American Time Use Survey (ATUS). Hours of work decreased as age increased, whereas time spent on various activities like sleeping, sports and leisure increased by age. For working men, time spent on doing household work increased with age, while for nonworking males a decline was seen in time for doing household work with respect to age. Moreover, use of time was also influenced by pandemic. The outbreak of COVID-19 forced people to stay at their homes, which affected the daily routines and activities of people. Pandemic has increased sleep duration (Cell Press, 2020). According to a study conducted during lockdown for COVID-19 in Belgium, adults were found to spend more time on physical exercise (Constandt et al, 2020). Average time spent on using the internet and watching TV and leisure activities was also increased during the quarantine. As people were bounded to their homes, they spent their time watching TV and involved themselves in leisure activities with their family members. Most of the people increased their internet usage, for using social media to be in touch with their friends. Social media and TV both are the sources for proving the latest information. Internet usage exponentially increased during the pandemic. Internet consumption increased by 47%. A significant increase was seen in watching TV and streaming services during corona virus pandemic. People used technology to ease anxiety and stress caused by the COVID-19 (Kiraly et al, 2020). Punyakaew et al. (2019) conducted a study that intended to find out the time use of people age 60 years residing in a village of Thailand. They found that most of the time spent by old people was in resting and sleeping.

Material and Method

The study was conducted on division Bahawalpur, Pakistan. It has three districts; district Bahawalpur, district Rahimyar Khan and district Bahawalnagar. Data was collected with the help of a questionnaire and 24-hour time use diary to gain a better insight about various activities in which retirees were usually involved. The activities in time diary were categorized accordingly. List of pensioners was taken from Accounts office of each district. The total population of retirees of division Bahawalpur in fiscal year 2018 was 10,919. The sample size was calculated using stratified random sampling. The calculated sample 386, was insufficient for the said research because of high expected response rate. Therefore, it was decided to take a 10% sample of the population, 1092. The data was collected in 18 months i.e., from February, 2019 to August 2020. In first phase data was collected from pensioners regarding their daily routines on a 24-hour time use diary, having intervals of 30 minutes starting from 12.00 am and ending at 11.59 pm, before pandemic. In second phase, time use diaries were refilled from the same respondents during Covid-19 outbreak. R programming was used for analysis of data. All activities by gender along with their t statistics and p values were determined and compared for the data before and during pandemic.

Results and Discussion

**Table 1 Activities by Gender along with their t statistics & P values
(Before COVID-19)**

Activity	Descriptive Statistics	Gender		t-Stats	P-value
		Men	Women		

Resting/Sleeping	Mean	451.87	451.92	0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	116.518	102.684		
Personal Care	Mean	41.64	38.60	-0.005	0.996
	Standard Deviation	22.371	17.636		
Eating	Mean	115.11	101.85	0.000	1.000
	Standard Deviation	42.692	42.957		
Travelling	Mean	22.55	18.95	0.003	0.998
	Standard Deviation	23.127	24.809		
Spending time with friends	Mean	53.21	16.89	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	63.049	41.002		
Spending time with family	Mean	157.79	149.34	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	143.273	140.510		
Physical exercise or playing sports	Mean	25.23	16.57	0.003	0.998
	Standard Deviation	37.956	30.299		
Using Internet including social networking	Mean	47.40	29.16	0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	63.272	48.268		
Talking on Phone	Mean	35.80	39.97	-0.002	0.998
	Standard Deviation	32.184	32.758		
Watching TV	Mean	107.52	111.61	-0.002	0.999
	Standard Deviation	93.470	101.985		
Reading (book, newspaper, magazine etc)	Mean	47.17	38.60	0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	60.818	58.769		
Housework	Mean	38.78	104.58	0.000	1.000
	Standard Deviation	64.841	121.613		
Shopping	Mean	39.97	32.10	0.000	1.000
	Standard Deviation	41.309	35.921		
Leisure activities	Mean	16.69	30.10	0.003	0.997
	Standard Deviation	42.121	55.659		
Outing	Mean	19.95	19.30	0.000	1.000
	Standard Deviation	42.034	46.327		
Religious activities	Mean	163.15	177.27	0.001	1.000
	Standard Deviation	103.531	100.362		
Social Work	Mean	15.34	10.70	0.003	0.998
	Standard Deviation	41.784	29.927		
Post retirement occupation	Mean	44.42	50.87	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	133.993	106.067		

The results from the above table 1 depict that both male and female respondents, spent an equal amount of time on sleeping. Male pensioners who were included in this study spent more time in their personal care than female

pensioners. Men spent averagely 115.11 minutes and females spent 101.85 minutes on eating in a day. The mean time spent by male pensioners on travelling was 22.55 minutes and for female pensioners, it was 18.95 minutes. Moreover, time spent by male pensioners with friends, family, exercising, reading and using the internet was 53.21, 157.79, 25.23, 47.17 and 47.40 minutes respectively. The time spent on these activities by males was much more than that of females. While the mean talking time of females on phone calls was more than that of male retirees.

As a matter of fact, females are fond of watching TV; it was also proved by this study. The mean time of females for watching TV was greater than male pensioners. Male retirees spent less time in house work and leisure activities, but more on social work. On the other hand, female retirees spare less time for social work and more time for house work and leisure activities. According to this study, male retirees spent a little more time on shopping as compared to female retirees. Both male and female retirees spent an equal amount of time on outing. Females spent 177.27 minutes and males spent 163.15 minutes on religious activities. Time spent on post-retirement occupation by female pensioners was more than the time spent by male pensioners.

Table 1 indicates that the p-value did not satisfy the criteria and it can be concluded that there is no association between gender and time spent on activities for data of collected before outbreak of COVID-19.

**Table 2 Activities by Gender along with their t statistics & P values
(During COVID-19 Lockdown)**

Activity	Descriptive Statistics	Gender		t-Stats	P-value
		Men	Women		
Resting/Sleeping	Mean	458.94	454.13	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	114.877	98.425		
Personal Care	Mean	41.52	38.50	0.003	0.998
	Standard Deviation	22.300	17.597		
Eating	Mean	129.77	120.10	0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	46.040	48.569		
Travelling	Mean	0.000	0.000	-	-
	Standard Deviation	0.000	0.000		
Spending time with friends	Mean	32.70	8.60	0.000	1.000
	Standard Deviation	49.586	26.267		
Spending time with family	Mean	195.85	191.54	0.000	1.000
	Standard Deviation	137.478	124.542		
Physical exercise or playing sports	Mean	27.46	18.67	0.003	0.998
	Standard Deviation	38.543	30.944		
Using Internet including social networking	Mean	56.74	39.65	-0.002	0.998
	Standard Deviation	63.977	51.883		
Talking on Phone	Mean	43.27	44.90	-0.002	0.998
	Standard Deviation	39.547	41.276		
Watching TV	Mean	117.42	123.88	0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	92.430	105.644		
Reading (book, newspaper, magazine etc)	Mean	53.05	49.30	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	62.269	64.112		
Housework	Mean	34.61	69.02	0.002	0.999

	Standard Deviation	56.540	91.585		
Shopping	Mean	0.000	0.000	-	-
	Standard Deviation	0.000	0.000		
Leisure activities	Mean	27.58	56.08	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	54.255	83.178		
Outing	Mean	0.000	0.000	-	-
	Standard Deviation	0.000	0.000		
Religious activities	Mean	173.68	181.57	0.000	1.000
	Standard Deviation	91.196	90.371		
Social Work	Mean	21.50	18.04	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	54.093	54.034		
Post retirement occupation	Mean	25.9	26.01	-0.001	0.999
	Standard Deviation	94.205	81.337		

Results from above table 2 signify that male pensioners approximately slept for 7.6 hours while female pensioners slept 7.5 hours daily during COVID-19 lockdown. There was no change seen in the time of personal care for both genders before and during COVID-19. Male pensioners spent more time than female pensioners on their personal care. Female retirees spent 2 hours whereas male retirees spent 2.16 hours on eating in a day averagely. Shopping, outing and travelling time, for both genders, was reduced to zero because of lockdown implementation in the country. On average, an equal amount of time was spent with family and talking on the phone call, by both genders during COVID-19 lockdown.

In spite of lockdown, male retirees couldn't resist themselves meeting their friends. Around 32 minutes were spent on meeting friends, by men. Women spent 8 minutes in a day meeting their friends. Male pensioners did the physical exercise for almost 27.46 minutes, while female pensioners did for 18.67 minutes, during the lockdown.

The average usage of the internet in a day by male pensioners was of 56.74 minutes and by females, it was 39.65 minutes. A minute difference of 6 minutes was noted in the mean time spent on watching TV by both genders. Male pensioners were more inclined towards reading books than females, as their average time for reading books was more than of female pensioners.

The study shows females spent more than an hour on household related activities, whereas males spent only half an hour on these activities. Men spent 27.58 minutes on their leisure activities and women spent 56.08 minutes on their leisure activities. Average hours spent by male and female pensioners on religious activities in a day during lockdown was 2.8 and 3 respectively. Time spent on social work by male pensioners was increased during the lockdown. Males spent approximately 21.5 minutes and females spent 18.04 minutes on social work. More or less, the same amount of time was spent on post-retirement occupation by both genders.

Table 2 shows that the p-value is not significant for any of the activity, hence indicating no significant effect of gender on time spent on activities.

Conclusion

The results of the present study precisely explore the nature of routine spent by the retirees in the division Bahawalpur, Pakistan. The focus of the current study was on gender wise comparison of time spent on various activities before and during pandemic. The above results show that pandemic abstained both male and female retirees from travelling, shopping and outing, whereas before pandemic a minor difference was seen in the time spent on travelling and leisure activities between male and female pensioners of division Bahawalpur. On average, both male and female retirees sleep/relax for almost 7.5 hours daily. Surprisingly, male retirees spent a little more time on their personal care and shopping than female retirees. Additionally, female pensioners spent more time on their post retirement occupation as compared to male pensioners before and during pandemic. The time spent on eating, exercising, internet, reading, social work and the time spent with friends and family was more of male retirees than that of female retirees. Internet usage was increased by male and female pensioners during Covid-19. As expected, female retirees spent more time talking on phone, watching TV and house work. Female pensioners spent their 3 hours, in an average, in a day on religious activities, whereas male pensioners spent 2.6 hours on religious activities.

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